

Experiments on vented hydrogen-air deflagrations: the influence of hydrogen concentration

Jin Guo ^{a,b}, Xuanya Liu ^c, Changjian Wang ^{d,*}

^a *College of Environment and Resources, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou 350116, PR China*

^b *State Key Laboratory of Fire Science, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230027, PR China*

^c *Tianjin Fire Research Institute, Tianjin 300381, PR China*

^d *School of Civil Engineering, Hefei University of Technology, Hefei 230009, PR China*

Corresponding author:

Changjian Wang chjwang@hfut.edu.cn

School of Civil Engineering, Hefei University of Technology, Hefei 230009, PR China

Abstract

The explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratios ranging from 0.4 to 6.0 was investigated in a small vented cylindrical vessel. The experimental results show that the maximum internal overpressure initially increases with an increase in hydrogen equivalence ratio up to approximately 1.6 and subsequently decreases. The discrepancy between the maximum internal overpressure and the vent burst pressure is significantly high for equivalence ratios ranging from 1.0 to 2.0 but low for very lean or very rich mixtures. Buoyancy has a significant effect on the evolution of the internal flame bubble for very lean hydrogen-air mixtures only. The speed of the external flame oscillates violently and its maximum value is achieved at a distance downstream from the vent. The maximum length of the flame ejected from the vent, which depends on the hydrogen equivalence ratio, may be underestimated by engineering models.

Keywords: Hydrogen; Explosion venting; Equivalence ratio; Overpressure; Flame

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is widely used in refining, fertilizers, chemical synthesis of materials etc., but it has a reputation of being dangerous owing to its extensive flammable range, low ignition energy, and high burning rate. Explosions might occur when hydrogen-air mixture is introduced in confined spaces; accordingly, an explosion vent may be installed to protect equipment or buildings against accidental internal deflagrations by means of quick pressure relief.

It has been established that hydrogen concentration has a significant effect on the reactivity of hydrogen-air mixtures and furthermore, on the overpressure of vented explosions ([Kumar et al., 1989](#); [Bauwens et al., 2012](#); [Kasmani, 2008](#); [Lowesmith et al., 2011](#); [Schiavetti et al., 2014](#); [Bauwens and Dorofeev, 2014](#); [Daubech et al., 2013](#)). The experiments performed by Kumar et al. ([1989](#)) with lean hydrogen-air mixtures in a vented spherical vessel demonstrated that the maximum pressure for central ignition increases with an increase in hydrogen concentration from 6 % to 20 % by volume. Bauwens et al. ([2012](#)) also determined that the peak pressure and burning velocity of the flame increase when hydrogen concentration increases from 12 % to 19 %. However, no significant increase in the maximum pressure for central ignition was observed with the increase of concentration of lean hydrogen-air mixtures ([Kasmani, 2008](#)). Lowesmith et al. ([2011](#)) investigated the effect of hydrogen concentration on explosion overpressures of methane/hydrogen mixtures. It was discovered that adding up to 20% hydrogen to methane resulted in a small increase in overpressure and a significant increase was observed when 50% hydrogen was added. Molkov et al. ([1999](#); [2000](#)) numerically investigated the explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures and the theoretical correlation they proposed predicted the deflagration pressures reasonably well.

On the other hand, when unburned hydrogen-gas mixtures are ejected out of a vented vessel, violent external combustion may occur. The formation and combustion of the external combustible cloud in

front of the vent were studied by seeding the gas mixtures in a vented vessel (Daubech et al., 2013; Proust and Leprette, 2010). It was observed that the expelled gas velocity is linked to the internal pressure, and the maximum velocity of the external flame occurs when the flame reaches the stagnation point of the leading edge of the cloud (Proust and Leprette, 2010).

Apart from the aforementioned research, some aspects of the effect of hydrogen concentration on the process of explosion venting have not been studied yet. For example, only lean (Kumar et al., 1989; Bauwens et al., 2012; Kasmani, 2008) and stoichiometric (Rocourt et al., 2014) hydrogen-air mixtures were investigated, but the extent of the effect of hydrogen concentration on pressure history and flame behaviors of hydrogen-rich mixtures still remains unclear, which also deserves detailed investigation because any concentration of hydrogen-air mixtures between the lower and upper explosion limits can be attained in real life—for example, when hydrogen is accidentally leaked in a confined space.

In this paper, experiments were conducted using hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratios ranging from 0.4 to 6.0 in a small vented vessel for the following reasons: first, to clarify the effect of the equivalence ratio on the maximum internal overpressure, and second, to investigate the behavior of internal and external flames before and after vent failure, especially the flame structure, flame speed, and length.

2. Experimental details

The experimental setup and procedures are similar to those adopted in our earlier work (Guo et al., 2015) and will be briefly described in this section. The setup consisted of a cylindrical vented vessel, flame image recording systems, pressure measuring system, and ignition unit. Both the inner diameter and length of the cylindrical vessel were 250 mm (volume $V = 12266 \text{ cm}^3$). A 10-cm-long vent duct with a cross section of 7 cm \times 7 cm was connected to the waist of the vessel. A diaphragm

was used as a vent cover to seal the exit of the short duct before the experiment. The moment of vent failure was obtained from the electrical circuit interruption owing to the breakage of a thin metal strip fixed to the diaphragm (Guo et al., 2016). The flame images inside and outside the vented vessel were captured by means of high-speed photography. Two piezoelectric pressure transducers (PCB 102B16) were used to record pressure history during the venting process—one (PT₁) was installed on the vessel wall opposite to the vent and the other one (PT₂) was installed on the duct wall 2 cm away from the vent cover. The hydrogen-air mixtures with equivalence ratios (ϕ) ranging from 0.4 to 6.0 were ignited at the center of the vessel with ignition energy of approximately 500 mJ. The initial pressure and temperature of the hydrogen-air mixture in all the experiments were 1 atm. and 300 K, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Pressure profile in vessel

Typical pressure profiles of the current experiments are shown in Fig. 1. As expected, ϕ has a critical effect on the pressure-time histories both in the vessel (PT₁) and at the duct exit (PT₂). Contrary to the pressure profiles with multi-peaks in existing research (Schiavetti et al., 2014; Rocourt et al., 2014; Bauwens et al., 2011), only one dominant internal pressure peak was observed for all the equivalence ratios tested. As shown in Fig. 1, PT₁ increases monotonically to its maximum value p_{\max} after vent failure and subsequently decreases to a negative peak owing to over-discharge (Molkov et al., 2006; Ferrara et al., 2006). Subsequently, a pressure peak with low amplitude can be distinguished for $\phi \geq 0.8$, which is due to the “residual” combustion in the vessel (Molkov et al., 2006).

Fig. 1. Typical pressure profiles for various ϕ .

Compared to PT₁, more pressure peaks form at the duct exit (PT₂). As shown in Fig. 1, the first pressure peak p_1 , which can always be observed, results from the burst of the vent cover (Rocourt et al., 2014; Guo et al., 2015). The second pressure peak p_2 , which can be observed only for $\phi = 1.0\text{--}2.0$, is mainly due to the fast burning rate of the internal flames. Furthermore, the third pressure peak p_3 , which appears approximately at the same time as the low amplitude pressure peak in PT₁, is also the result of afterburning in the vessel (Molkov et al., 2006).

Special attention is paid to the maximum internal overpressure p_{\max} , and the relationship between p_{\max} and the vent burst pressure p_v ; further, the method to determine p_v was described in our previous studies (Guo et al., 2015; Guo et al., 2016). As shown in Fig. 2, p_{\max} first increases and subsequently decreases with an increase of ϕ . The peak value of p_{\max} appears at approximately $\phi = 1.6$; in fact, the variation of p_{\max} is relatively small when ϕ ranges from 1.2 to 2.0. Notably, the excess pressure $p_{\max} - p_v$, which is in the range of several kilopascals for methane-air mixtures (Guo

et al., 2016), is significantly high especially for $\phi = 1.0$ – 2.0 owing to the high burning rate. Therefore, for vented hydrogen-air deflagrations, the formation of stoichiometric and fuel-rich mixtures should be prevented as much as possible; simultaneously, larger vent area is required to reduce p_{\max} .

Fig. 2. p_{\max} and $p_{\max} - p_v$ vs. ϕ .

In addition, acoustic oscillation of the internal pressure, which results from the interaction between the combustion process and acoustic waves (McCann et al., 1985; Wingerden and Zeeuwen, 1983; Ferrara et al., 2008), is clearly observed only in the case of $\phi = 0.6$ as shown in Fig. 3. Violent oscillation can be more easily observed by differentiating the pressure-time profile. As shown in Fig. 3, the oscillation amplitude of $dPT1/dt$ increases gradually and subsequently decreases, and the frequency of oscillation ranges from approximately 1600 Hz to 2000 Hz. The oscillation frequency can be estimated using $f_a = c/2L$ (Blevins, 1979), where c is the speed of sound in the vessel and L is the length of enclosure. Accordingly, L can be replaced by vessel diameter (25 cm), and c can be calculated using $c = \sqrt{\gamma RT}$, where r is the specific heat ratio, R is the gas constant, and T is the temperature of the gas mixture in the vessel. Schlieren images show that, when the oscillation occurs, the flame front nearly touches the wall of the vessel. Thus, the parameter c of the burned gas mixtures, which is approximately 910 m/s, should be used to estimate f_a . This yields a

typical acoustic oscillation frequency of approximately 1920 Hz, which agrees with the measured values (1600–2000 Hz).

Fig. 3. Acoustic oscillation for $\phi = 0.6$

3.2 Flame behavior in vessel

In this study, the evolution of the internal flame was captured using a high-speed schlieren system, and typical schlieren images are presented in Fig. 4. It was observed that for very lean hydrogen-air mixtures, for example $\phi = 0.4$, the flame bubble is deflected upward from the ignition location owing to the buoyancy effect as discovered in constant volume explosions (Bychkov and Liberman, 2000; Li et al., 2013). However, the buoyancy effect can hardly be observed for $\phi \geq 0.6$, because the combustion time is significantly reduced owing to the quick increase in burning speed when ϕ increases from 0.4 to 0.6.

Fig. 4. Schlieren images of the internal flame.

On the other hand, flame cellularity can be easily observed for ϕ ranging from 0.4 to 6.0 in current experiments. Especially, in the case of lean hydrogen-gas mixtures, flame cellularity can be observed in an earlier stage of flame evolution, whereas it appears much late in the case of hydrogen-rich mixtures. As shown in Fig. 5, many cusps appear on the flame surface for $\phi = 0.8$, resulting in the flame bubble appearing quite rough. Although complete cellularity occurs for $\phi = 2.0$, the flame surface remains relatively smooth. When ϕ reaches 3.0, cellular structure appears only in the bottom half of the flame bubble, and significantly fewer cells can be observed in the case of $\phi = 5.0$.

Fig. 5. Microstructure of the flame surface when flame enters the duct.

Owing to the buoyancy effect of the flame bubble and cusps on the flame surface, it is difficult to determine the location of the flame front for lean hydrogen-air mixtures. Therefore, in this study, the location of the flame front and the flame speed evaluated from schlieren images only for a rich gas mixture are investigated because the flame surface remains relatively smooth even after the occurrence of flame cellularity, and the location of flame front and the flame speed as a function of time for $\phi = 4.0$ are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Location of flame front and flame speed vs. time for $\phi = 4.0$.

As shown in Fig. 6, the flame propagates toward and away from the vent at a nearly identical speed of approximately 8–17 m/s within several milliseconds after ignition. With further expansion of the flame bubble, the flame surface stretches to the vent owing to the abrupt decrease of the flame passage area, and the flame speed quickly increases to approximately 43.5 m/s. Notably, the oscillation amplitude of the flame speed propagating away from the vent decreases from the appearance of cellular structure on the flame surface to the failure of vent cover, and simultaneously the rate of pressure rise in vessel increases. The quick increase in rate of pressure rise is due to the increase in flame area owing to the development of small cusps and troughs (Lowesmith et al., 2011) and flame elongation (Catlin, 1991).

3.3 Propagation of external flame

The vented external flames of gases (Daubech et al., 2013; Rocourt et al., 2014; Molkov et al., 2006) and dusts (Castellanos et al., 2013; Yan et al., 2015) have been experimentally and numerically investigated. In current experiments, external flames can hardly be observed for $\phi = 0.4$ and 0.6 owing to low flame luminosity, and typical flame images of the external flames recorded by a high-speed camera are presented in Fig. 7. After vent failure, violent jet combustion occurs outside the vent and the external flame extends quickly to its maximum length L_{\max} ; subsequently, the flame length decreases gradually. During the process of venting, several mach disks can be observed in front of the vent in some cases, as a result of the supersonic outflow, can be observed in some cases.

(a) $\phi=1.2$

(b) $\phi=4.0$

Fig. 7. Direct photos of external flames.

Fig.7 also demonstrates that the size of external flame increases when ϕ increases from 1.2 to 4.0. Particular attention should be paid to L_{\max} and the maximum diameter of the external flame D_{\max} , which can be used to estimate the hazardous area around the vent. EN 14994 (2007) suggested that L_{\max} can be calculated using $L_{\max} = 5\sqrt[3]{V}$ for volume of vessels ranging from 0.1 m³ to 50 m³, and little or no effect of explosion reactivity on L_{\max} was found for explosion venting of dust (Wingerden,1993). However, the results of current experiments show that ϕ also has critical effect on L_{\max} . As shown in Fig. 8, L_{\max} increases from approximately 59 cm ($\phi = 0.8$) to 159 cm ($\phi = 4.0$) and subsequently decreases with a further increase of ϕ , which yields a ratio of L_{\max} to $\sqrt[3]{V}$ ranging from approximately 2.6 to 6.9.

Fig. 8. L_{\max} and D_{\max} vs. ϕ .

Daubech et al. (2013) established that the maximum diameter of an external combustible bubble for a large vent size is approximately twice the width of the vent, and a jet structure rather than a bubble of expelled unburned gas appears when the vent size is reduced. Similarly, axisymmetrical jet combustion is observed in the current vessel with a vent coefficient $V^{2/3} / A_v \approx 11$, and D_{\max} increases monotonically from approximately 17 cm ($\phi = 0.8$) to 53 cm ($\phi = 6.0$).

Fig. 9 presents the flame speed versus the location of flame front evaluated according to direct flame images. The maximum flame speeds are achieved not at the exit but at a distance downstream from the vent. For example, the flame speed attains a maximum value of 604 m/s at approximately 59 cm away from vent for $\phi = 4.0$. Fig. 9 also shows that the velocity of the external flame oscillates violently especially for hydrogen-rich mixtures. A possible reason is that the turbulence generated at the edge of discharged gas mixtures and stationary air will cause entrainment of air in the outflow and lead to dilution. When the flame propagates into a region where hydrogen concentration approaches stoichiometric value, the flame speed increases, and thus, oscillation of the flame speed occurs.

Fig. 9. Flame speed vs. distance to vent.

The aforementioned experimental results demonstrate that flames ejected from a vent with a very high speed can attain a maximum length larger than the estimated value, which may cause a secondary disaster. Hence, sufficient safety distance around the vent is required to prevent nearby

personnel and equipment from being injured; on the other hand, measures such as flameless venting (Holbrow, 2013) are also worthy of consideration, which will be investigated in our future work.

4. Conclusions

Pressure histories and flame behaviors inside and outside a vented vessel were experimentally investigated in the process of explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures from a small vented vessel. The maximum internal overpressure initially increases with an increase in hydrogen equivalence ratio from 0.4 to approximately 1.6 and subsequently decreases with a further increase of hydrogen equivalence ratio up to 6.0. The maximum internal overpressure is much larger than the vent burst pressure for equivalence ratios ranging from 1.0 to 2.0. Acoustic oscillation was observed with a frequency range of approximately 1600–2000 Hz when the equivalence ratio was 0.6.

Buoyancy has a negligible effect on the internal flame bubble when the equivalence ratio is larger than 0.4. Cellularity of the internal flame occurs in an earlier stage of flame propagation in the case of leaner hydrogen-air mixtures. Flame ejects from vent at a high speed, and the maximum speed of the external flame is attained at a distance downstream from the vent. Hydrogen equivalence ratio has a significant influence on the maximum length of the external flame, which may be underestimated by engineering models.

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